

LIBRARY- INFORMATION ACTIVITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract: In this article, the library-information activity system is an area that directly affects the economic, social, cultural, and scientific production of our republic. Of course, these effects may not be felt immediately, but they will have an impact over the years. This article discusses the management system and laws of library-information activities.

Key words: document, library, library-information activity, book, service, system, scientific activity.

Introduction:

"Library-information activity" is a complex socio-cultural system, which is made up of small systems that are tightly connected with each other and have their own characteristics and patterns of development. Before moving on to the laws of development and specific features of the library-information activity, we will dwell on the structural systems that make up this system and their functions in the system¹.

Library-information activity consists of six structural subsystems, which are:

- Library - networks of information institutions;
- Completing the funds of library and information institutions;
- Organization of library - information service;
- Training and retraining of personnel, improving their qualifications.
- Organization of scientific research works;
- They are scientific-methodical works.

The current state of library and information activities is directly dependent on the current state and development of these components. If any of the above components lag behind the others, it directly affects the general development of library and information activities.

The network system of library and information institutions is one of the main systems in library and information activities. It is known that not only in our republic, but also in many developed countries, libraries are divided into several branches, which indicates that they belong to different offices and organizations. We have several branches of libraries, and their management is carried out by the higher management bodies of these branches. By transferring the libraries of the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the Center for Secondary Special Vocational Education of OUMTV, the Ministry of Public Education Information and resource centers were established at secondary special education

¹ Akhunjonov E. Library science, archival science, theory and history of library science.-Tashkeht.: Tafakkur, 2011.

institutions and general education schools. Information-library centers subordinate to the Communications and Information Agency of Uzbekistan were established on the basis of regional scientific and universal libraries. In addition, almost every field has its own library networks:

Ministry of Health, Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management, Ministry of Defense, etc. The development of the library network of these offices and organizations is at different levels, and the function of libraries is considered based on the main tasks of these offices and organizations.

Accordingly, all library networks, on the one hand, satisfy the needs of society members for general cultural and professional information, and productive spending of free time, and on the other hand, which office and organization belongs to this library serves to fulfill the main tasks of this organization.

It can be seen that the activities of any library are aimed at meeting the needs of society members for one or another type of information, but they organize their tasks based on the tasks of the offices and organizations they are subordinate to. At the same time, the active operation of libraries depends to a large extent on the demands and interests of the citizens living in this area for library services and information.

In the library-information activity, the library-fund collection system is also important, in which each library and information institution creates a library fund or information resources based on the task it has set for itself. The activity of the sub-system of the collection of the library fund is directly related to book publishing in the country and the creation of other types of information. At the same time, it directly depends on how the library employees understand the main task of this library, and the level of studying the interests of readers. Also, the economic and financial situation of the library plays a significant role in the completion of the library fund, the functioning of the library and information institution in general.

It should also be noted that all types of libraries can be divided into independent and non-independent libraries in terms of financial support. Independent libraries are libraries that have their own funds and manage their financial and economic affairs through their own account numbers. This includes national libraries, special network libraries, republic scientific universal libraries. The rest of the libraries are considered independent libraries and directly depend on the financial situation of the offices and organizations they are subordinate to. From this point of view, it is natural that the collection of library funds is different.

The library-information service sub-system is one of the sub-systems of the library-information activity system. At present, service to consumers in libraries and information institutions is carried out individually and in groups with primary documents, books, magazines, newspapers and other sources of information, bibliographic materials, inside and outside the library itself. Direct service is provided in the library itself through subscriptions and study halls, while non-stationary service is provided through mobile libraries and book lending forms.

The personnel training and retraining system includes training of personnel for librarianship in higher and secondary specialized educational institutions, improvement of their qualifications, seminars, internships, and roundtable discussions organized in large libraries. The activity of this system is related to another sub-system of the library work system, the scientific-research system. The system includes departments of higher

educational institutions, research departments of large libraries. The sub-system of scientific-methodical support includes republican network scientific libraries, methodical service of information-library centers, and methodical service departments of large branch libraries.

The library-information activity has a global goal: to ensure free access to information, to introduce people to the masterpieces of the homeland and world culture, and to satisfy the population's ever-growing information and spiritual needs. Sub-systems of the complex and multi-level library-information activity system, in turn, have their own special tasks performed by the system. For example, the sub-system of personnel training and retraining produces highly qualified specialists for the field. The sub-system of assembling and organizing the fund carries out the work of providing the necessary publication products and information materials for the library. It is important to develop the above subsystems. Then the tasks of the library-information activity will be fully fulfilled.

There are laws and specific aspects of the development of the library-information activity system. First of all, let's talk about the concept of legality. Legitimacy is the reestablishment of existing objective relationships between phenomena in nature and society. In the library-information activity, it is the relationship between the components, as well as between the library-information activity system and the society. In the following years, we will briefly touch on them, summarizing their scientific opinions in this field.

One of the main laws in the development of library and information activities is the law of mutual cooperation between libraries and information institutions. According to this law, libraries and information institutions should work together in different ways to make the use of their information resources available to consumers. In fact, if we look at the history, for many years, libraries and information institutions have been working in cooperation with each other to satisfy the needs of the population for information and spirituality.

The second principle is to increase the social effectiveness of the use of information collected in the Library-information system. According to this law, the library-information activity system and its separate parts, including libraries, try to satisfy the interests of the whole society and the individual consumer to the maximum extent, with the information collected in their funds. The third law of librarianship is dynamism, that is, changeability of library-information activity. Library-information activity is not a frozen system, it is a constantly changing and developing system. This situation is evident in today's practice. As an example, it is enough to see the development process of library and information activities in the twentieth century².

Today, the process of informatization of library-information activities is being carried out. New information technologies, the creation and use of electronic databases, the implementation of mutual cooperation of libraries through network technologies, the introduction of the world librarianship process and the world information exchange process are being implemented. All this means that librarianship is developing dynamically and is on the path of development that meets modern requirements.

The fourth principle is the democratization of library and information activities. According to this law, the library-information activity is not only the main tool that implements continuous education and independent education, develops a person's worldview

² Yesimov.T.B Formation and development of librarianship in Uzbekistan. - T.: 1994.

and thinking, but also provides information to all citizens, regardless of their social status, nationality, race, political opinion. It is noted that it is a democratic source. We must emphasize that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes the rights of citizens to use information sources.

The law of democratization of librarianship ensures the organization of the network system of library and information institutions, free implementation of the main library - information service. The legitimacy of the democratization of library and information activities is reflected in some aspects of the management of this field, such as the activation of librarianship aspects and the activities of associations, the regular reporting of library managers to their readers, the organization of more efficient service to library users demands and interests are manifested in regular study and so on.

The fifth law in library-information activity is the law of dialectical unity of national statehood and internationalism. According to this law, the library and information activities of each country reflect the specific characteristics of that country. At the same time, it is also international because it reflects universal human values and the achievements of science, culture, and art achieved in the world through the information activities of the library.

The sixth law is the law of advantage of an individual approach in the provision of library and information services. According to this law, the main task of libraries and information institutions should be to satisfy people's spiritual and informational needs by approaching them individually. This law has been the main principle in all periods of the history of library-information activity.

The seventh law is that the library-information activity is related to the social, economic, political and cultural life of the society and obeys the general laws of the development of the society.

In the history of the development of library and information activities, we see that the library and information activities are also changing due to changes in the economic conditions of society and political revisions. A vivid example of this is the changes in recent years. In the period of transition to a market economy, political, ideological, spiritual and cultural changes in our country, library and information activities are also changing. The right to engage in economic activities for library and information institutions, to organize the use of legal and physical entities in their book fund on the basis of a contract, to introduce paid services, to cooperate with foreign institutions and organizations, and for other purposes a wide path was opened. At the same time, the democratic reforms in our country have a great impact on the library and information activities. In particular, this is evidenced by the fact that the libraries themselves determine the contents of their work, the library network is moving from centralization to decentralization, and various restrictions are abolished.

Another important law is law of proportional development of library and information activities. This law notes the need for proportional development of all sub-systems of library-information activities. Without it, the industry cannot function fully and effectively, for example, the lag of any small system, for example, the lag of the fund assembling or personnel training system, will quickly be reflected in the activity of the entire system, reducing its effective operation, books and information causes difficulties in providing services.

Along with the above-mentioned laws, the library-information activity has its own characteristics. One of the unique features of the library-information activity is that people's interests lie at the basis of its activity. Society, public and personal interests have an active

influence on the state of library-information activity and its development as a system. Another characteristic aspect of the library-information activity is the direct contact of the library staff with the population groups with different interests and requirements, working groups, actual and potential readers. That is why they try to study the motivations of consumers' demands for books and information and to satisfy them as much as possible.

Conclusion:

Another feature that has influenced the development of library and information activities is the development of the culture of each country, the level of spiritual inquiries of the population. The higher the culture and spirituality of the population, the more intensely librarianship will develop. At the same time, the development of library and information activities directly affects the cultural, spiritual and intellectual development of the citizens of this country.

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